

Innovations in service experiences; the AT-ONE method

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Summary

We live in a service economy and more than 70% of total value added in the OECD countries comes from services. In Norway, eight out of 10 new jobs are created within service industries and three out of four employees work in service provision. Services are not the same as products, yet we often find companies designing services using product-based methods with the result that the design of the user experience is not given the focus it deserves. This paper describes a method, AT-ONE, which is being developed to assist in the early stages of the service innovation process. Its focus is to design innovative and engaging service experiences, and at the same time, encourage design thinking in the organisation. The paper describes the background for the method, the method itself and first results from its use within several service providers.

Background

Services play a key role in the economy

Industries that deliver help, utility, experience, information, or other intellectual content have expanded rapidly in recent decades and now account for more than 70% of total value added in the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries. Market-based services (that is, excluding those typically provided by the public sector, such as education, health care, and government) account for 50% of the total and have become the main driver of productivity and economic growth in OECD countries, especially as use of IT services has grown.

Service Innovation is poorly researched

Considering its key role for value creation in today's economies, service innovation has been poorly researched. Whilst product innovation and innovation systems have been well researched, particularly during the past 10 years, service innovation has had little focus (Methlie and Pedersen 05). Research that has been carried out on services has focussed upon "Services in Innovation" rather than "Innovation in Services" (Methlie and Pedersen 05).

Service innovation differs from product innovation

The term New Service Development (NSD) has been coined as a mirror to the term new Product Development. Much of the research into service innovation has focussed upon the differences between products and services and how NSD should be treated as a separate branch of innovation, rather than the

process itself. The ACM recently called for the creation of a new discipline, that of Services Science, (ACM 06) claiming that:

“the opportunity to innovate in services, to realise business and societal value ... has never been greater. The challenges are both the multidisciplinary nature of service innovation...as well as the lack of formal representations of service systems”. Spohrer and Riecken (06)

Services are characterised as having distinct differences from products, each with consequences for innovation and development. Table 1 summarises these differences. At present innovation methods do not adequately take these differences into account.

Services are...	Characterised by	Consequences for innovation
Intangible	Services are experiential	Increased focus upon designing and managing expectations and user experiences
Time-based	A dialogue between service provider and customers	Importance of consistency based upon a brand ‘promise’
Delivered across multiple touch points	Multi-channel delivery	Importance of holistic approach to service design, often crossing organisational boundaries
Simultaneous	Produced and consumed at the same time	Ability to design tailored individual experiences

Table 1: Characteristics of services and their consequence for innovation

Innovation in services is becoming customer- and experience-centric

The increased focus upon service innovation has been paralleled by an increasing awareness of the importance of the customer dimension of service provision. Demos (a UK Government think-tank) show that the service sector has focussed its development upon commodotisation of services through chasing economies of scale, producing what they describe as “a fundamental disconnect between services and people” (Demos 06). They cite the need to rethink service innovation in a customer-centric way, and show how product differentiation is now based upon a clear focus upon luxury, differentiation and perceived uniqueness. They claim that services are lagging behind products in terms of radical innovations and show that “people have changed faster than service organisations” (Demos 06). Demos show that expanding choice and growing wealth have created needs that are not covered by todays services. They cite todays modern need for meaning and recognition, autonomy, control and participation as central aspects to todays consumer, with services lagging behind this change. This raises difficult issues for companies offering services who are “struggling to escape the historical legacy of mass provision”. These conclusions are supported by Cullum (06) who shows that:

- 81% of people had a bad experience purchasing services in the previous year, citing words such as distant, clinical and uncaring
- 70% of people consider companies are out of touch with their customers
- Consumer switching levels have increased by 52% in the past 5 years

Grönroos (2000) claims that a new paradigm of service provision has arrived, one based upon interactions between service providers and their customers. This paradigm is based upon customer experiences over the long term, and not just upon simple, singular exchanges of value.

Reibstein (04) highlights the benefits of providing good customer service experiences:

highly satisfied Starbucks customers patronised the chain for more than eight years, made 86 visits per year and spent more than \$3,000 over that time. He calculated the difference between satisfaction and dissatisfaction to be \$2,800 per customer

Service-Design is becoming established as a new area of innovation

Service-design is emerging as a multi-disciplinary area for research and development

The term service-design is emerging as a response to industries' needs to improve service provision. It is a multi-disciplinary area that focuses upon innovation through the design of customer experiences, and is centred upon design-innovation using a services frame of mind rather than a product frame of mind.

Service design is defined as:

Design for intangible experiences that reach people through many different touch-points, and that happen over time. (www.servicedesign.org)

As an area of R+D it has its roots in countries that are strong service economies, such as USA, UK, Italy and Germany. It has no specific discipline at its core, and can be described as the meeting point of:

Interaction design (Saffer 06),

Experiential marketing (Schmitt (03), Smith and Wheeler,02),

Services marketing (Van Looy et al 03)

Innovation management (Smith and Reinertsen 95),

Customer-centred Innovation (von Hippel 05),

Branding (Wolff Olins 95 and Aaker 02)

Design management (Hollins, 94, Cooper 04)

Design leadership and Design thinking (Best 06)

The need for a method for service-design

The increasing focus upon innovation in services using a customer focusses approach requires a design process that highlights and bases itself upon designing user experiences and service encounters. At present, no coherent method exists for this, although in the product design area, value-based design methodology is beginning to influence product development methods (eg Lærdahl (01), Tollestrup (04)). Common to many

“recent” methods, these approaches focus upon emotional, symbolic and idealistic values of products within a multi-disciplinary framework. They also focus upon vision driven development and the use of facilitated workshops to speed development and raise quality.

The AT-ONE method for service-design

AT-ONE is a method to assist service-design at the early phases of the service innovation process. AT-ONE focuses upon the elements that are different between products and services, and has a clear user, and user experience focus.

Each of the letters of AT-ONE relate to a potential source of innovation in services:

A - New combinations of ACTORS who together provide the service

T - Coordination and development of TOUCH-POINTS between customer and service

O - The design of what the service is actually OFFERING

N - The NEEDs that the service satisfies

E - The EXPERIENCE that the service gives the customer

AT-ONE integrates existing knowledge, but its combination of knowledge elements is new.

As a designer or researcher reading this, you will probably be familiar with many of the elements utilised in AT-ONE. It does not introduce radically new tools to the development process, rather it combines best practice from design and research. Its relevance and newness comes from the combination of elements and their introduction to the design process, not the elements in themselves.

AT-ONE is aimed at the service industry

AT-ONE has, as a goal, to produce a method that service providers will find easy to grasp and easy to implement. Its goal is to assist service providers that do not have a strong customer focus but wish to introduce one, or service providers with a customer focus wanting to improve the first stages of innovation. Our experience is that the service-industry still does not have a customer focus but is moving towards this, and that AT-ONE fulfills a need within the industry itself. AT-ONE is not specifically aimed at the research community.

At the fuzzy front end of the innovation process

The AT-ONE project focusses upon service innovation at the front end of the development process. This has often been termed the fuzzy front end (Smith & Reinertsen 98) and describes the phase at the start of the NSD (New Service Design) process often called preliminary planning or early concept development. This is the area within service innovation that is least researched and which has fewest support tools. Most service management texts assume a concept as a start point and many organisations have implemented very effective stage-gate processes for the latter phase of development, eg the Cooper stage-gate process (Cooper 86). The earliest phases offer the greatest opportunity for transformational innovation and 66% of life-cycle costs are decided here, whilst only about 5% of development costs are utilised (Berliner and

Brimson, 88). Innovation is particularly cost-effective at this stage, and it is often termed the bargain basement of life cycle development - improved focus here gives very high returns (Smith & Reinertsen 98). It is increasingly being focussed upon by designers, as they are given a more explorative and open brief (Sanders and Stappers 08)

Design thinking as a foundation for the method

The term ‘design thinking’ relates to the introduction of design methods and culture into fields beyond traditional design and links design and transformative innovation. Stanford’s new Design School, the d.school, based on joint programmes between business and design, is one of the places where the notion of design thinking has emerged. One of the key aspects of design thinking is that of abductive thinking (Margolin, V. & Buchanan, R. (1995), Liedtka yy), the designers focus upon a vision of possibility. It is this ability, together with the ability of design to synthesise disparate needs and rapidly produce tangible concepts that forms one of the core elements of the AT-ONE method. Within the AT-ONE process it is visible in that designers have responsibility to plan, facilitate and participate in innovation workshops with the role to encourage abductive thinking within the group and as a means of developing and documenting/visualising new service innovations.

Figure 1. Different roles for the designer through time. Design thinking relates to the role of design in company vision and strategy (based upon Valtonen 2007).

The 'service journey' as a customer-focussed timeline

AT-ONE uses the service journey (also called user journey) as a means of structuring customer points of experience over time. The service journey is a chronological mapping (from the customer point of view) of a service encounter. It divides the service encounter into separate stages and gives a customer view into the service delivery process. Several of the design agencies and consultancies that specialise in designing

customer experiences studied by Voss and Zomerdijk (2007) used the journey perspective to analyse current experiences and design new ones. Several firms had developed a technique for mapping customer journeys, among them “The Brand Touchpoint Wheel” (Dunn and Davis .

Personas as core elements

The AT-ONE method utilises personas as a means of identifying and introducing a user focus to the innovation process, and personas are available for all development workshops. Personas are not the only form for user representation in the process. They are used in addition to other forms of user input, such as observation, interviews and co-design, which are integrated into the N (need) part of the method. The project bases itself primarily upon the persona lifecycle as described by Pruitt and Adlin (06).

Evidencing as an output form

In the fields of industrial design and interaction design, prototyping and modeling are well defined processes that help the designer, client and potential user evaluate the concept at an early phase of development (eg. Capjon 04).

Jane Fulton Suri developed the idea of “Experience Prototyping” through practice in IDEO, a large design consultancy, and defined the term to describe the use of one interface, or “touch-point” (Suri 00). This idea of experience prototyping for services has been developed further by service-design consultancy LiveWork under the title ‘evidencing’, in which several media channels are prototyped, together with contextual-supportive content, storytelling and scenarios. Evidencing is an attempt to quickly prototype intangible service experiences. The goal of evidencing is not to specify design elements, but to conjure up user experiences of a new service, at a very early stage of the development process. To do this, design elements are shown in context, linking service journey elements to touch-points, content and experiences.

Figure 2: Evidencing is a means to conjure up experiences early in the process (photos: Livework/AHO)

AT-ONE is run as a series of workshops

The AT-ONE process is run as a series of workshops, each with a focus upon the letters A,T,O,N,E, described below. The workshops can be run separately or can be combined, such that the method is scalable. Initial evaluations have evaluated the method scaling from one day for all letters, to a half day per letter.

Each letter is planned individually and in relation to each other. The metaphor for the workshops is that each is a different ‘innovation lens’ used to view and develop the same project challenge. By using five different lenses, the goal is to stretch and explore the solution space as early in the design process as possible.

Each workshop has three phases, and is based upon commonly used creative processes (Isaksen et al 00):

- Startpoint:- establishing a common knowledge platform for participants (1/5th of workshop)
- Divergence:- exploring and generating ideas and solutions
- Convergence:- synthesis, ranking and decision-making

Figure 3: AT-ONE utilises a workshop approach

A key aspect to the workshops is the combination of participants representing stakeholders from the client organisation, domain-specific expertise and service designers.

The Actor workshop

The basis of the Actors workshop is recent developments in the area of value networks as an alternative to the value chain. Value networks are more prevalent in services, and describe how actors together create value for the customer.

Their key strategic task is the reconfiguration of roles and relationships among this constellation of actors in order to mobilize the creation of value in new forms and by new players. And their underlying strategic goal is to create an ever-improving fit between competencies and customers.

(Normann and Ramirez 93)

Figure 4: Actor networks create value with customers. Adding or removing actors can radically change a service offering and the service experience.

The Actors workshop investigates users as co-creators of value (von Hippel 05, Sanders and Stappers 08) and upon innovating value networks (Johanson et al 99). One key aspect here is to replace an organisations company-centred mapping of actors to one in which the customer is at the centre of the network and to consider new actors to the value network to give improve user value.

The Touch Point workshop

The touch point model is based upon the touch point brand model by Dunn and Davis (05). They describe how touchpoints can be segmented into three categories that generally represent the different dimension of a brand's relationship with a customer. In a service context they can be defined as: 1) Experience touchpoints when planning or preparing for a service transaction. 2) Service transaction touchpoints during the transaction and. 3) Post transaction touchpoints

Figure 5: Touch-points connect users to the service during the service journey and are the tangible expression of a service offering.

The touch-point workshop maps out different touch-points during the service journey and compares and contrasts the use and quality of touch-point interactions. It looks for opportunities to introduce potentially new and more effective touch-points, remove weak touch-points and to coordinate the user-experience across touch-points in relation to brand message and user needs.

The Offering workshop

The approach taken on brand offering is based upon the model from Aaker (02), particularly brand personality. In a design perspective this has been adapted by Karjalainen (04)) and slightly adapted for the project. The offering workshop focusses upon the projected offering from the company, based upon the companies brand DNA. It also relates this to the cultural negotiation that takes place in the interface between projected offering and perceived offering. The brand megaphone model adapted from Ellwood (2000) is used as a model for the Offering workshop.

Figure 6: Offering looks at the negotiation that takes place between projected and perceived offering

Figure 7: The brand megaphone shows the relation between company DNA and how this is experience through different touch-points (based upon Ellwood 00)

The goal of the Offering workshop is to evaluate the service offering in relation to the brand DNA and to identify any mismatch. Such mismatches can then be corrected through the alteration of the service offering, or through the development of new services. Several tools have been developed to assist this alignment process,

The Need workshop

The need workshop takes a user-centred design approach to explore user-needs. It uses personas as a vehicle for introducing a user perspective (Pruitt and Adlin 06) and adds user input from a wide selection of user-centred methods, such as interviews, observation, participatory design sessions as outlined on usability net (www.usabilitynet.org/tools/methods). The need workshop has EN ISO 13407 Human-centred design processes for interactive systems, as its approach (ISO13407 99)

Figure 8: The needs workshop looks at both emotional and functional needs and attempts to uncover hidden needs

The Experience workshop

The experience workshop builds upon the recent developments in the design of experiences. It combines approaches from consumer behaviour (Ratneshwar et al 00, Hansen and Christensen 07), the experience economy (Pine and Gilmore 98), Experiential Marketing (Schmitt 03) and Experiential Branding (Gad 01, Gobe 01).

Figure 9: The experience workshop attempts to define a desired experience and reverse engineer to service touch-points, offering and actors. We have found that a common vocabulary of experience words is needed.

EPG Experience Positioning Grid

Figure 10: Example of a tool used in the experience workshop, the experience positioning grid is used to map customer experiences at each stage of the service journey

Several tools have been developed to assist in using experiences as a start-point for design. Ideally we aim to design service-experiences and reverse engineer the organisation and service to be able to reliably produce the desired experience. This can be termed an experience “pull” approach. In practice we have found this difficult due to the lack of suitable tools for adequately designing and describing a desired

experience. We hope to develop an experience “pull” method during the next few years, but until it is available, we are using a set of “push” tools that relates customer experiences to the service journey. One such tool is the Experience Position Grid (shown above). Another tool is the experience gap analysis, simply describing today's service experience with the desired experience.

Evaluation of the method

The AT-ONE method is being developed and evaluated as part of an ongoing research project jointly funded by industry partners and the Norwegian Research Council (NFR). As part of this project, AT-ONE workshops will be run two times per year for each industrial partner. So far, two major iterations of the method have been carried out, one within a student course and one within a relevant industrial project.

The results are promising and the AT-ONE method scores highly when evaluated by participants from service providers. Detailed results were not available at the time of writing this article, but initial evaluations are positive. The method receives positive feedback in terms of typical innovation metrics :

- number and breadth of ideas generated
- relevance and quality of ideas
- relevance of themes covered and knowledge created
- a desire to use the method again for other service innovation processes
- a desire to implement the results

In terms of acceptance within the participating organisation for the AT-ONE method, the method and the results have been presented to the innovation boards within participating organisations and to top management. This indicates a desire to promote the method within the organisation. Further validation and evaluation work will be carried out as the project progresses.

Reflections upon the use of the method highlight several interesting aspects:

- designers have a central role in the workshops
- facilitation of workshops is a critical success factor
- the use of tangible aids during workshops aids the process and outcome
- the careful design of workshop elements (aids, forms, notes) is important
- the method is effective in terms of minimising client time in terms of results obtained, but requires a considerable amount of planning and follow-up
- involving client stakeholders with designers and experts in each discipline is a strong combination

Further development

The method is being continually updated as part of a research project looking into service innovation (www.service-innovation.org) which continues until 2010. The method will be documented and will form the core of a service design initiative from the Norwegian Design Council. Further development will formalise the method, evaluate its scalability and develop a set of tools for each of the workshop letters.

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